

MUHANDISLIK

& IQTISODIYOT

№2

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

2026 fevral

Milliy nashrlar

OAK: <https://oak.uz/pages/4802>

05.00.00 - Texnika fanlari

08.00.00 - Iqtisodiyot fanlar

Google Scholar

OPEN ACCESS

ULRICHSWEB[™]
GLOBAL SERIALS DIRECTORY

Academic Resource Index
ResearchBib

ISSN INTERNATIONAL STANDARD SERIAL NUMBER INTERNATIONAL CENTRE

CYBERLENINKA

OpenAIRE

ROAD

INDEX COPERNICUS INTERNATIONAL

BASE

Crossref

НАУЧНАЯ ЭЛЕКТРОННАЯ БИБЛИОТЕКА LIBRARY.RU

ISSN: 3060-463X

РЭУ.РФ
РОССИЙСКИЙ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЙ УНИВЕРСИТЕТ
ИМЕНИ Г.В. ПЛЕХАНОВА
ТАШКЕНТСКИЙ ФИЛИАЛ

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Elektron nashr, 609 sahifa.
2026-yil, fevral

Bosh muharrir:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, DSc, professor

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Shakarov Zafar G'afarovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori, PhD, dotsent

Tahrir hay'ati:

Abduraxmanov Kalendar Xodjayevich, O'z FA akademigi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Mahammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor,

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Botirali Roxataliyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

Jo'raeva Malohat Muhammadovna, filologiya fanlari doktori (DSc), professor.

Yusupov Maxamadamin Abduxamidovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor

Kalonova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (PhD), dotsent

Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanzakovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi (DSc), professor.

Karimova Nilufar Sadirdin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Norboyev Odil Abrayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Mirzayev Kulmamat Djanzakovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

Karimova Nilufar Sadirdin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

muhandislik & iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari
- 10.00.06 – Qiyosiy adabiyotshunoslik, chog'ishtirma tilshunoslik va tarjimashunoslik
- 10.00.04 – Yevropa, Amerika va Avstraliya xalqlari tili va adabiyoti
- 08.00.01 – Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 – Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 – Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 – Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 – Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 – Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 – Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 – Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 – Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 – Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 – Marketing
- 08.00.12 – Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 – Menejment
- 08.00.14 – Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 – Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 – Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 – Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil 28-avgustdagi 360/5-son qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

1. Toshkent shahridagi G.V.Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
2. Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
3. Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
4. Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
5. Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
6. Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
7. Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
8. Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
9. Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

RIVOJLANGAN MAMLAKATLAR BANKLARIDA RISK-MENEJMENTNING TASHKILYI MODELLARI.....	26
Madaminov Bekzod Allayarovich	
“HUDUDGAZTA‘MINOT” AJ DA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN LOYIHALAR SAMARASI	32
Shukurillaev Jahongir Botir o‘g‘li	
HARBIY XIZMATCHI AYOLLARNING MAXSUS KIYIM SIFATIGA QO‘YILADIGAN DASTLABKI TALABLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH	37
Abduraxmanova N.D., Mirtolipova N.X., Nasirullayeva G.S.	
СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ НЕСПЕЦИФИЧЕСКОГО ЯЗВЕННОГО КОЛИТА У ДЕТЕЙ	42
Закирова Бахора Исламовна, Каримов Достон Рустам угли	
ОЦЕНКА ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЯ ФИСКАЛЬНЫХ И КРЕДИТНЫХ ИНСТРУМЕНТОВ НА РЫНКИ ВЫСОКОЛИКВИДНОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ И ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫХ МОНОПОЛИЙ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН.....	48
Бекзод Умматов	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ СИСТЕМ БУХГАЛТЕРСКОГО УЧЕТА В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ: СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ ЭКОНОМИКО-СТАТИСТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА.....	55
Вахидов Азизжон Саиджонович	
SUG‘URTA FAOLIYATIDAGI MOLIVAVIY RISKLAR: BAHOLASH VA MINIMALLASHTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI	58
Xalikulova Shirin Utkir qizi	
“ANDIJONDONMAHSULOT” AJ MISOLIDA XARAJATLARNING STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV HISOBİ: AMALIY TAHLIL VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH TAVSIYALARI	62
Xayitboyeva Laylo Oybekovna	
XORIJİY MAMLAKATLARNING NORASMIY IQTISODIYOT DARAJASINI PASAYTIRISHDAGI TAJRIBASI	66
Alimardonov G‘ayratjon Nuraliyevich	
XO‘JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARDA BARQARORLIK HISOBOTLARI AUDITINI SHAKLLANTIRISH	72
Xolikov Ravshan Anvar o‘g‘li	
PUL - KREDIT SIYOSATINING TRANSMISSION MEXANIZMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH	76
Obidova Zilola Ikromjon qizi	
HOMILADORLIK DAVRIDA AYOLLARDA UCHRAYDIGAN GESTOZLI KATARAL GINGIVITNI KOMPLEKS DAVOLASHNI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH	81
Nomurodova Farangiz Lazizovna	
AGRAR KORXONALARDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHDA INVESTITSIYA MEXANIZMLARINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGI VA RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘NALISHLARI	87
Egamberdiyev Abdujabbor Xusanovich	
YOSHLAR TADBIRKORLIGI VA KICHIK BIZNES IQTISODIYOTINI TA‘MINLASHDA INFRATUZILMALARDAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI	92
Mirzatov Baxtiyor Toxirovich	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARI FAOLIYATINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASINING MAZMUNI VA TAMOIYILLARI	96
Mavrulov Ravshan Nematjonovich	

УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫМИ КОММУНИКАЦИЯМИ В ПРОЕКТАХ	101
Носирова Гулираъно Абдулазиз кизи	
DAVLAT BUDJETI JARAYONIDA MONITORING VA MOLIYAVIY NAZORATNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	107
Yax'yayeva Dilfuza Bagdatovna	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA KICHIK KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	111
Axmedov Sanjar Temur o'g'li	
RAQAMLI MOLIYA TEXNOLOGIYALARI EVOLYUTSIYASINING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI VA YUZAGA KELISHI MUMKIN BO'LGAN XATARLAR TAHLILI	117
Ko'chimov Jahongir Shuxrat o'g'li	
GAZ VA GAZ KONDENSATINI YIG'ISH VA TAYYORLASH TIZIMLARI UCHUN ZAMONAVIY LOYIHALASH USULLARI TAHLILI	123
Abdirazakov Akmal Ibragimovich Namozov Og'abek Maxmud o'g'li	
AGILE PROJECT MANAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL ERA: STRATEGIES, FRAMEWORKS, AND BEST PRACTICES FOR SUCCESS	128
Utkirova Maftuna Murodjon qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON EKSPORTYOR KORXONALARINING YANGI BOZORLARGA CHIQISHIDA FAOL MARKETING VOSITALARIDAN FOYDALANISH HOLATI VA MUAMMOLARI	134
Baqoyev Sunnatillo Burxon o'g'li	
TADBIRKORLIK FAOLIYATIGA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI JORIY ETISHNING ILMIIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	139
Salaydinov Shodiyor Nizom o'g'li	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA INVESTITSION LOYIHALARNI BOSHQARISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING TASHKILIIY-IQTISODIY JIHA TLARI	144
Qurbonov Jasurbek Pozilovich	
OPTIMIZATION OF ROADSIDE AUTO CAMPING SITES (REST AREAS) ON HIGHWAYS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: INFRASTRUCTURE GAPS AND CORRIDOR-BASED EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	150
Akramov Akbarjon Akmal ugli	
QURILISH KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION MARKETING YONDASHUVLARINING AHAMIYATI	156
Aminov Abbas Mo'minboy o'g'li	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA AHOLI ISH BILAN BANDLIGI SAMARADORLIGINI IFODALOVCHI KO'RSATKICHLAR	160
Abdusaidov Akmal Abduvaliyevich	
MINTAQADA XUSUSIY TIBBIYOT MUASSASALARIDA MARKETING STRATEGIYASI	165
Yakubov Temur G'anibekovich	
AHOLI DEMOGRAFIK JARAYONLARINI IFODALOVCHI STATISTIK KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMI	169
Siroj Zarina Rustambekovna	
AXBOROT MAHSULOTLARI BIZNESINING YAIM VA BANDLIKKA TA'SIRI: EKONOMETRIK TAHLIL	176
Abdullayev Abdulla Fayzulla o'g'li	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA SOG'LIQNI SAQLASH TIZIMINI IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI	181
Ziyodullayev Qahramon	
ЭНЕРГОЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ: ПОЛЬЗА ДЛЯ ЭКОНОМИКИ И ЭКОЛОГИИ	185
Хамдамова Гавхар Абсаматовна	
O'ZBEKISTONDA EKSPORTNI RAG'BATLANTIRISHNING MOLIYAVIY VOSITALARI VA ULARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI	191
Mamatov Baxodir Quldoshovich	

KO'P QIRRALI VALLARNING SHAKLLANTIRISH METODLARI VA USULLARINI TAHLIL QILISH	197
<i>Xasanov Bobirmirzo Maxmudali o'g'li, Valixonov Dostonbek Azim o'g'li, Alibekov Rasulbek Qanotbek o'g'li</i>	
MINTAQA SANOATINING TARKIBIY TRANSFORMATSIYASI VA UNNING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRINI EKONOMETRIK MODELASHTIRISH	205
<i>Abdinazarov Xusan Shaymanovich</i>	
RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA SHAROITIDA SUG'URTA BOZORINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH	209
<i>Nomozova Qumri Isoyevna</i>	
XALQARO STANDARTLAR TALABLARI ASOSIDA AUDITORLIK TEKSHIRUVINI TASHKIL ETISHNING ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	216
<i>Akromov Shohrux Shuhrat o'g'li</i>	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATIDA XIZMATLAR SOHASINING RIVOJLANISHNI TARTIBGA SOLISH TIZIMI	221
<i>Achilova Firuza Kurbanovna</i>	
BANK MENEJMENTIDA INKLYUZIV MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI, TAMOYILLARI VA STRATEGIK AHAMIYATI	225
<i>Rajabov Oybek Panjievich</i>	
MINTAQADA OLIY TA'LIM TIZIMINING ISHSIZLIK DARAJASIGA TA'SIRINI EKONOMETRIK MODELASHTIRISH	229
<i>Rustamov Jasurbek Ravshanbek o'g'li</i>	
MAISHIY XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA INNOVATSION KLASTER MODELINI JORIY ETISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI	235
<i>Normurodova Zebo Eshmaxmatovna</i>	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA INVESTITSIYA FAOLIYATINI BOSHQARISH	240
<i>Xatamov Nurbek Ochildiyevich, Sharifi Abdul Fatah</i>	
MOLIYAVIY REJALASHTIRISHNING AMALDAGI MUAMMOLARI VA ULARNI YECHIMI YUZASIDAN TAKLIFLAR	245
<i>Pardayev Jamshid Muzaffarovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANKLARI LIKVIDLIK RISKLARINI BAHOLASH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	251
<i>Sulaymanov Samandarboy Adhambek o'g'li</i>	
O'ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RISKLARNI BOSHQARISH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	257
<i>Karimov Shohrux Boydulla o'g'li</i>	
"O'ZBEKISTON TEMIR YO'LLARI" AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATINING HISOBOTLARINI XALQARO STANDARTLARGA TRANSFORMATSIYA QILISH	262
<i>Astanov Zafar Murodillayevich</i>	
QARAMA-QARSHI AYLANUVCHI IKKI ROTORLI SHAMOL TURBINASINING MATEMATIK MODEL	266
<i>Pirmatov Nurali Berdiyevich, Bekishev Allabergen Yergashevich, Saodullayev Abror Saypullayevich, Qurbonov Najmiddin Abduxamidovich</i>	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA KICHIK VA O'RTA BIZNESNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INSTITUTIONAL VA INVESTITSION MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	272
<i>Norboev Sarvar Azodovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TRANSPORT SOHASIDA FAOLIYAT YURITAYOTGAN TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINING IQTISODIY AHAMIYATI	277
<i>Jaloliddinov Anvar Jaloliddin o'g'li</i>	
ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN'S MAIN ECONOMIC INDICATORS AND GDP GROWTH	283
<i>B.Beknazarov</i>	

SOTISH JARAYONIDA INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA MARKETING TADQIQOTLARINING INTEGRATSIIYASI	288
Abduxalilova Laylo Tohtasinovna	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В АУДИТЕ ФИНАНСОВОЙ ОТЧЕТНОСТИ: ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЙ И УЗБЕКСКИЙ КОНТЕКСТ	294
Мегноров Алмардон Абдирахмонович	
RISK MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN UNCERTAIN ECONOMIC ENVIRONMENTS: A GLOBAL COMPARATIVE STUDY	302
Nigmatova Malika	
OLIIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MOLIIYAVIIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI.....	307
Hamrayev Maqsudjon Saidaxmadovich	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHNI TA'MINLASHDA AHOLI BANDLIGINI OSHIRISH MASALALARI	311
Mamajonova Gulbaxor Toxirjon qizi	
АВТОМАТИЗАЦИЯ АУДИТОРСКИХ ПРОЦЕДУР НА ОСНОВЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ: ВЛИЯНИЕ НА КАЧЕСТВО АУДИТОРСКИХ ЗАКЛЮЧЕНИЙ	316
Киличева Ф.Б.	
MAISHIY TEXNIKA EKSPORTIDA YASHIL IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIKNI BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY-METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI	320
Kushmanova Mahbuba	
GAZ TA'MINOTIDA YO'QOTISHLARNI KAMAYTIRISHNING IQTISODIY ASOSLARI	324
Xamidov Xayriddin Faxritdinovich	
DAVLAT AKTIVLARINI XUSUSIYLASHTIRISHNING MINTAQA IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRINI BAHOLASH (QASHQADARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA).....	329
Sharapov Farrux Shomuratovich	
КРИТЕРИИ ОТБРАКОВКИ ЭКСТРУЗИОННЫХ АЛЮМИНИЕВЫХ ПРОФИЛЕЙ ГРУППЫ ALMGS1 ПО МАКРОСТРУКТУРНЫМ ПРИЗНАКАМ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ УСЛОВИЯХ	333
Ибрахимов Фаррухжон Фарходович	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIDA DEBITORLIK QARZLARI VA FAKTORING OPERATSIYALARI HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	336
G'oziyeva Mokhira Rustamovna	
KULTIVATOR YUMSHATKICH PANJALARI O'TMASLANISH DARAJASINING ISH KO'RSATKICHLARIGA TA'SIRI	345
Quvondiqov Yoqub Tursunbaevich, Nuraliyev To'liqin Alimardanovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARINI BOSHQARISHDA INNOVATSION STRATEGIYANI RIVOJLANTIRISH BO'YICHA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR	352
To'g'onov Ibroximxo'ja	
TMK KORXONASI SHAROITIDA R6AM5 MARKALI TEZKESAR PO'LATDAN TAYYORLANGAN PARMA UCHUN TERMIK ISHLOV BERISH REJIMI	358
Djalalova Sevara Toxtamuratovna	
РОЛЬ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В РАЗВИТИИ ИНКЛЮЗИВНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ	362
Шоев Алим Халмуратович	
TRANSFORMATSIYA VA XUSUSIYLASHTIRISH OMILLARINING BANK SAMARADORLIGI KO'RSATKICHLARIGA TA'SIRI	367
Umirzoqova Aziza Olim qizi	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH	372
Ismatov Raxmatilla Oltinovich	
RAQAMLI TO'LOV TIZIMLARI TADBIRKORLIK SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILI SIFATIDA.....	376
Yoqubjonov Ibrohim G'olibjon o'g'li	

BANK TIZIMIDAGI AKTIVLARINING UNUMDORLIGINI OSHIRISH BO'YICHA STRATEGIK YONDASHUVLAR	379
Sadikov Q.M.	
СЦЕНАРНОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭНЕРГОЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ОТРАСЛЕЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА В УСЛОВИЯХ НЕОПРЕДЕЛЁННОСТИ И СТРУКТУРНЫХ ПРЕОБРАЗОВАНИЙ	383
Муслимова Ф.С., Хашимова Н.А.	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TIBBIY XIZMATLARNI TAQDIM QILISHNING INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLARI	390
S.M. Raximova	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARI AXBOROT-RESURS MARKAZLARI FAOLIYATINI STRATEGIK BOSHQARISH MODELI	395
Qurbanova Muazzam Fazliddinovna	
IQTISODIYOTNING TRANSFORMATSİYALASHUVI JARAYONIDA INVESTITSION KREDITLASHNING TAHLILI	399
Tuxsanov Eldor Dilmurod o'g'li	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA EKSPORTNI RAG'BATLANTIRISH MASALALARI	404
Abdug'aniyev Murodjon Shavkat o'g'li	
XO'JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARNING INNOVATSION FAOLIYATINI INVESTITSİYALAR YORDAMIDA QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH	408
Baxriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
FRANSUZ TILIDA FE'L SEMANTIKASINING KO'PMA'NOLILIK VA BIRMA'NOLILIK ASPEKTLARI	412
Jo'rayeva Malohat Muhammadovna, Bekmetova Munisa Karimbayevna	
QORAQALPOG'ISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA ASOSIY KAPITALGA KIRITILGAN INVESTISIYALARDA CHET-EL INVESTISIYASI VA KREDITLARINI ROLI	418
Sultanov Anvar Abdullaevich	
INSON QON TOMIRLARINING TARMOQLANISHINI L-SISTEMALAR ASOSIDA HOSIL QILISH ALGORITMNI ISHLAB CHIQUISH	423
Boliyeva Dilrabo Nurbek qizi	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT LOYIHALARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK (DXSH)NING AHAMIYATI	429
Ergashev Axmadjon Maxmudjon o'g'li	
NAMANGAN VILOYATIDA TURIZM SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING STRATEGIK YO'NALISHLARI	434
Otaylor Usmonaliyev	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA VALYUTA ARBITRAJI VA UNING MOHIYATI	440
Yaxyayev Ziyodilla Lutfullayevich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN ALOQA SOHASINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	443
Mirzaraximova Aziza Azimdjanovna	
DON VA UN MAHSULOTLARINI QAYTA ISHLASH KORXONALARIDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINI BOSHQARISH XUSUSIYATLARI	450
Boyjigitov Sanjarbek Komiljon o'g'li	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA TUXUM ISHLAB CHIQUARISHNING JORIY HOLATI TAHLILI	454
Ismoilov Zuhridin Sayitqulovich	
ZAMONAVIY TURAR-JOY ME'MORCHILIGIDA MILLIYLIK VA AN'ANAVIYLIKNING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI	459
Toshniyozov Otabek Hakimovich	
MARKAZIY QIZILQUM FOSFORIT RUDALARIDAN QIMMATBAHO KOMPONENTLARNI KOMPLEKS AJRATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI	464
Eshonqulov Uchqun Xudaynazar o'g'li, Ruzibayeva Dildora Akramovna, Xushvaqtova Dilshoda Shavkat qizi	

BANKLARDA CHAKANA KREDITLASH JARAYONLARINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH TARTIBI	470
<i>Axmedova Dilrabo Kurbondurdi qizi</i>	
TADBIRKORLIK VA KICHIK BIZNESNI QO‘LLAB-QUVVATLASHNING XALQARO MODELLARI HAMDA ULARNING AMALIY AHAMIYATI	476
<i>Nodirbek Shavkatovich Mirzaaxmedov</i>	
DAVLAT FUQAROLIK XIZMATIDA XOTIN-QIZLARNING BOSHQARUV KARYERASI: MOHIYATI, ZARURIYATI VA ILMIY-NAZARIY ASOSLARI	483
<i>Abduraxmonova Feruzabonu</i>	
ASOSIY KAPITALGA INVESTITSİYALARNI MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING RIVOJLANAYOTGAN MAMLAKATLAR TAJRIBALARI	489
<i>Xoshimov Sobir Murtazayevich</i>	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI ISHLAB CHIQARUVCHI KORXONALARDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINING TASHKILIY TUZILMASINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH	495
<i>Uzakova Umida Ruziyevna</i>	
OLIY TA‘LIMNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH SAMARADORLIGI VA PROFESSOR-O‘QITUVCHI–TALABA NISBATI O‘RTASIDAGI IQTISODIY BOG‘LIQLIK.....	502
<i>Dusanov Salim Mamarasulovich</i>	
МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ ВНЕДРЕНИЯ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В СИСТЕМЫ AML: АНАЛИЗ ПРАКТИК ВЕДУЩИХ БАНКОВ И СТРАН СНГ	507
<i>Рашидов Авазбек Рахимович</i>	
BOJXONA TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISHDAGI MAVJUD MUAMMOLAR TAHLILI	516
<i>Radjapova Latofat Sardorovna</i>	
DEFORMATSİYALANUVCHAN STANDART CHIZIQLI QATTIQ (STANDARD LINEAR SOLID MODEL, SLS) MODEL ISHLAB CHIQISH VA SONINI TAHLIL QILISH	523
<i>Ahmadov Ilhom Aktam o‘g‘li, Faxriddinova Rayhona Vahobjon qizi, Rustamova Ruxsora Kamtar qizi</i>	
ВЛИЯНИЕ КЕРАМИЧЕСКИХ КОМПОЗИЦИОННЫХ ПОКРЫТИЙ НА ТЕПЛОВУЮ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ КАМЕННОГО ТЕПЛОАККУМУЛЯТОРА В СОЛНЕЧНО-АССИСТИРОВАННЫХ БИОГАЗОВЫХ УСТАНОВКАХ	530
<i>Д.М. Жураханов</i>	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA ISLOMIY MOLIYA TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING KELAJAKDAGI IMKONIYATLARI.....	537
<i>Akbarov Husniddinjon Mo‘ysin o‘g‘li</i>	
MAHALLIY BUDJETLARNI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA OCHIQLIKNI KUCHAYTIRISH	544
<i>Xolmirzayev Ulug‘bek Abdulazizovich, Normatov Joxongir Murodillayevich</i>	
DON MAHSULOTLARI TARMOG‘IDA ISHLAB CHIQARISH QUVVATLARIDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	548
<i>Aipova Iroda Ikramovna</i>	
BUXORO VILOYATI SANOATI ISHLAB CHIQARISHINING TARMOQ TARKIBI DINAMIKASI VA UNDAGI O‘ZGARISHLAR TAHLILI	554
<i>Toshov Mirzabek Hakimovich</i>	
TEMIR YO‘L TRANSPORTINING RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH MEZONLARI	560
<i>Nurxo‘jayeva Xilola Hakimxo‘jayevna</i>	
СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В УПРАВЛЕНИИ УГОЛЬНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТЬЮ НА ОСНОВЕ УСТОЙЧИВОСТИ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА	568
<i>Teshaboyev To‘lqin Zakirovich, Muradov Botir Xayat</i>	
IQTISODIYOT TARMOQLARIDA SUV ISTE‘MOLINING BOSHQARUVINI RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	578
<i>Karimov Anvarjon Muqumjonovich, Turg‘unov Muhammadaziz Baxtiyorjon o‘g‘li</i>	
SUV RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA MOBIL ILOVALAR ASOSIDA SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	584
<i>Karimov Anvarjon Muqumjonovich, Uzakov Sirojiddin Djuraboyevich</i>	

SUN'IY INTELLEKT VA IQTISODIYOTNING O'ZARO ALOQADORLIGI	591
Sobirov Abdurasul Abdugafarovich	
IDENTIFICATION OF WEAVING STRUCTURES IN PILE FABRICS	596
Bahrom Baturovich Dautov, Bakhtiyor Yormakhmatovich Abduganiyev, Erkin Shamsiddinovich Rayxonov, Nazar Kilichov Bafoevich	
INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO ENSURING FINANCIAL STABILITY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS.....	602
Otajanova Shahnoza Shuhratovna	

INNOVATIVE APPROACHES TO ENSURING FINANCIAL STABILITY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS

Otajanova Shahnoza Shuhratovna

Tashkent State University of Economics

Phd student

ORCID: [0009-0007-0428-5014](https://orcid.org/0009-0007-0428-5014)

Email: shahnozaotajanova830@gmail.com

Abstract. This article analyzes the potential of using innovative solutions to ensure financial stability in commercial banks. In light of recurring global financial crises, rapid digital transformation, and increasingly stringent international regulatory requirements, banks are compelled to adopt new strategic approaches. The study investigates the implementation of Basel III standards and the integration of artificial intelligence (AI), big data analytics, blockchain technology, and RegTech tools in commercial banking operations. Drawing on both international practices and the experience of Uzbekistan, the research evaluates the effectiveness of innovation-driven strategies in strengthening financial stability. The findings demonstrate that modern technologies enable early risk detection, process automation, and more efficient management of capital adequacy and liquidity. Based on this analysis, recommendations are provided to support the development of innovation-based financial resilience in the banking sectors of emerging economies.

Keywords: financial stability, commercial banks, innovative solutions, artificial intelligence, blockchain, big data, risk management, Basel III, RegTech, liquidity.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada tijorat banklarida moliyaviy barqarorlikni ta'minlashda innovatsion yechimlardan foydalanish salohiyati tahlil qilinadi. Takrorlanib kelayotgan global moliyaviy inqirozlar, tezkor raqamli transformatsiya va tobora qat'iy lashib borayotgan xalqaro regulativ talablar sharoitida banklar yangi strategik yondashuvlarni joriy etishga majbur bo'lmoqda. Tadqiqot Basel III standartlarini amalga oshirish hamda sun'iy intellekt (AI), katta ma'lumotlar tahlili (big data), blokcheyn texnologiyasi va RegTech vositalarini tijorat banklari faoliyatiga integratsiya qilish jarayonlarini o'rganadi. Xalqaro tajriba hamda O'zbekiston amaliyoti asosida innovatsiyaga yo'naltirilgan strategiyalarning moliyaviy barqarorlikni mustahkamlashdagi samaradorligi baholanadi. Tadqiqot natijalari zamonaviy texnologiyalar erta risk aniqlash, jarayonlarni avtomatlashtirish hamda kapital yetarliligi va likvidlikni samarali boshqarish imkonini berishini ko'rsatadi. Tahlil asosida rivojlanayotgan iqtisodiyotlarda bank sektorining innovatsiyaga asoslangan moliyaviy barqarorligini rivojlantirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: moliyaviy barqarorlik, tijorat banklari, innovatsion yechimlar, sun'iy intellekt, blokcheyn, katta ma'lumotlar, risk boshqaruvi, Basel III, RegTech, likvidlik.

Аннотация. В статье анализируется потенциал использования инновационных решений для обеспечения финансовой устойчивости коммерческих банков. В условиях повторяющихся глобальных финансовых кризисов, стремительной цифровой трансформации и ужесточения международных регуляторных требований банки вынуждены внедрять новые стратегические подходы. В исследовании рассматриваются вопросы внедрения стандартов Basel III, а также интеграции технологий искусственного интеллекта (AI), анализа больших данных

(big data), блокчейн-технологий и инструментов RegTech в деятельность коммерческих банков. На основе международного опыта и практики Узбекистана оценивается эффективность инновационно-ориентированных стратегий в укреплении финансовой устойчивости. Результаты исследования показывают, что современные технологии способствуют раннему выявлению рисков, автоматизации процессов и более эффективному управлению достаточностью капитала и ликвидностью. По итогам анализа предложены рекомендации по развитию инновационно-ориентированной финансовой устойчивости банковского сектора развивающихся экономик.

Ключевые слова: финансовая устойчивость, коммерческие банки, инновационные решения, искусственный интеллект, блокчейн, большие данные, управление рисками, Basel III, RegTech, ликвидность.

INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary financial landscape, commercial banks play a vital role in maintaining economic stability by serving as key intermediaries in the allocation of capital and the provision of financial services. However, the global financial crises of the past two decades, particularly the 2008 financial meltdown, exposed significant vulnerabilities in banking systems, emphasizing the importance of robust financial stability frameworks.

Ensuring the financial stability of commercial banks has become increasingly complex due to rapid digitalization, evolving regulatory environments, and emerging financial risks. Traditional approaches to risk management are no longer sufficient in isolation. In this context, the adoption of innovative technologies and international regulatory standards—such as the Basel III framework—has become essential to reinforcing banks' resilience to systemic shocks.

Modern tools such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data analytics, blockchain technologies, and regulatory technologies (RegTech) are transforming how banks assess creditworthiness, manage market and operational risks, and maintain adequate liquidity and capital buffers. These innovations enable early risk detection, real-time monitoring, and enhanced decision-making processes, which are crucial for long-term financial sustainability.

This paper explores the integration of these innovations into commercial banking practices, with a focus on ensuring financial stability. By analyzing international best practices and the specific case of Uzbekistan's banking sector, the study aims to assess the effectiveness of these strategies and provide policy recommendations for innovation-driven banking reform in emerging economies.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The question of how to ensure financial stability in commercial banks has been the subject of growing academic and policy attention, particularly in light of the vulnerabilities exposed by successive global financial crises. Traditionally, financial stability has been framed around key indicators such as capital adequacy, liquidity coverage, asset quality, and profitability (Allen & Wood, 2006). However, the dynamic and increasingly digitized nature of the financial ecosystem demands a rethinking of these conventional paradigms[13].

A significant body of literature has emerged around the role of international regulatory frameworks—most notably the Basel III standards—in reinforcing the resilience of the banking sector. The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (2011) introduced revised standards focusing on strengthening capital bases, introducing countercyclical capital buffers, and enhancing short- and long-term liquidity measures (LCR and NSFR). These reforms are widely considered a foundation for macroprudential stability[14].

Nonetheless, recent research has emphasized that compliance with regulatory standards alone is not sufficient. Berger and Bouwman (2013) argue that capital strength must be supplemented by data-driven risk identification tools and flexible internal governance[3]. Demirgüç-Kunt and Detragiache (2002) further highlight institutional quality and the rule of law as key determinants of systemic stability in banking.

The role of financial innovation has gained increasing scholarly interest. Technological advancements—particularly in the areas of artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), blockchain, and big data analytics—are reshaping the risk management frameworks of commercial banks. According to Frost et al. (2019), AI-powered algorithms can improve credit scoring, detect fraud, and optimize asset allocation in real time. Similarly, Arner, Barberis, and Buckley (2017) introduced the term RegTech to describe the use of digital tools for regulatory compliance, suggesting that these innovations help reduce operational risk and increase transparency[1].

Recent empirical research further supports the growing importance of financial innovation in transforming commercial banking. The integration of FinTech solutions into traditional banking systems has been shown to enhance operational efficiency, improve credit risk assessment, and strengthen overall financial performance.

For instance, Thakor A.V. (2020) emphasizes that digital technologies such as artificial intelligence and big data analytics improve screening mechanisms and reduce information asymmetry in lending markets. Similarly, Vives X. (2019) argues that digital transformation increases competition and incentivizes banks to adopt innovative risk management frameworks to remain sustainable in evolving financial ecosystems[11, 12].

The case of Uzbekistan and other developing economies has increasingly attracted scholarly and institutional attention, particularly in the context of financial sector modernization and digital transformation. Recent assessments by the International Monetary Fund (IMF, 2023) and the World Bank (2022) highlight that banking sector reforms in Uzbekistan—especially digitalization, improved supervisory frameworks, and strengthened risk management systems—have contributed to enhanced financial stability and institutional resilience. The introduction of automated credit risk assessment tools and improved liquidity monitoring mechanisms has supported better governance practices within commercial banks[5, 6].

The operations of systemically important banks (SIBs) in emerging markets have received significant scholarly and regulatory attention, particularly in the context of digital transformation and evolving risk profiles. The Basel Committee on Banking Supervision (BCBS, 2011; 2013) emphasizes that strengthened capital quality, enhanced supervision of risk-weighted assets (RWA), and stricter prudential standards are essential for safeguarding financial stability in systemically important institutions. Higher loss-absorbing capacity requirements for global and domestic SIBs are designed to reduce systemic risk and improve resilience during financial stress[2].

The literature reveals a broad consensus that achieving sustainable financial stability in commercial banking requires a holistic integration of regulatory discipline, institutional reform, and technological innovation. However, significant gaps remain in the empirical evaluation of these innovations, particularly in emerging markets where institutional capacities and digital infrastructure are still developing. This paper contributes to this discussion by synthesizing insights from global practice and analyzing how innovation-led strategies are reshaping financial stability paradigms in the commercial banking sector of Uzbekistan.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research utilizes a comparative and analytical methodology to evaluate the financial stability of commercial banks in Uzbekistan within the framework of international standards such as Basel III. A mixed-methods approach was applied, combining both quantitative and qualitative data analysis to ensure a holistic understanding of the issue. The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Secondary data were collected from official financial reports of Uzbek commercial banks, including Xalq Bank, Trustbank, Asaka Bank, Agrobank, and others. International comparisons were drawn from Basel Committee on Banking Supervision documentation and performance indicators from major global banks in countries such as the United States, Germany, and Japan.

The primary indicators used to assess financial stability include: Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Tier 1 Capital Ratio, Leverage Ratio, Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR), Net Stable Funding Ratio (NSFR). These indicators are aligned with the Basel III standards and are utilized to analyze both short-term liquidity positions and long-term solvency.

The research also examines the implementation of modern risk management tools such as:

- Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML): used in predicting and mitigating credit and operational risks.
- RegTech (Regulatory Technology): applied to ensure compliance and automate internal control mechanisms.
- Cybersecurity and Information Systems: for operational risk reduction and secure banking infrastructure.
- Big Data Analytics: utilized for customer risk profiling and creditworthiness assessment.

A benchmarking method is used to compare the financial indicators of selected Uzbek commercial banks with those of developed countries' banks. This enables the identification of gaps and areas where Uzbek banks can enhance their financial resilience.

A scoring model was applied to assess the financial performance of each bank across five key dimensions: capital strength, asset quality, liquidity, profitability, and risk management sophistication. Quantitative data were statistically processed using Excel and SPSS tools to identify patterns, trends, and correlations.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The empirical assessment was conducted on five major commercial banks in Uzbekistan—Xalq Bank, Trustbank, Asaka Bank, Agrobank, and Hamkorbank—focusing primarily on their capital adequacy and liquidity metrics, as defined under Basel III standards. Two key indicators were used:

- Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR): A measure of a bank's capital relative to its risk-weighted assets.
- Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR): A measure of a bank's ability to withstand short-term liquidity disruptions (Table 1).

Table 1. Key Financial Stability Indicators (CAR and LCR) of Selected Commercial Banks in Uzbekistan¹

Bank	CAR (%)	LCR (%)
Xalq Bank	12.5	110
Trustbank	13.2	115
Asaka Bank	11.8	108
Agrobank	14.0	120
Hamkorbank	12.0	112

The quantitative results are summarized in the Table 1. Agrobank leads among the sampled institutions with the highest CAR (14.0%) and LCR (120%), reflecting strong capital reserves and excellent short-term liquidity management. Trustbank follows closely with healthy indicators (CAR: 13.2%, LCR: 115%), suggesting sound risk management practices and financial planning.

Asaka Bank, while still compliant with Basel III minimums, showed relatively lower ratios, indicating potential vulnerabilities in capital allocation or liquidity strategy. Hamkorbank and Xalq Bank demonstrated stable performance with CAR levels between 12–12.5% and LCR levels slightly above the minimum standard of 100%, showing reliable but improvable liquidity buffers.

Beyond capital adequacy and liquidity ratios, additional performance metrics offer deeper insights into the operational efficiency and asset quality of commercial banks. These include Return on Equity (ROE), Non-Performing Loans (NPL) ratio, and the Cost-to-Income ratio (Table 2).

Table 2. Operational Performance Indicators of Selected Commercial Banks in Uzbekistan²

Bank	ROE (%)	NPL (%)	Cost-to-Income Ratio (%)
Xalq Bank	14.5	3.2	48
Trustbank	16.2	2.7	45
Asakabank	12.8	4.0	52
Agrobank	17.3	2.5	43
Hamkorbank	13.6	3.5	50

The ROE results indicate that Agrobank (17.3%) and Trustbank (16.2%) achieved the highest profitability, reflecting efficient use of shareholders' equity. Asaka Bank had the lowest ROE (12.8%), which might be attributed to higher operating expenses or lower asset returns. The NPL ratios show that Agrobank (2.5%) and Trustbank (2.7%) maintain the best loan portfolio quality, while Asaka Bank (4.0%) and Hamkorbank (3.5%) have relatively higher credit risk exposure. In terms of operational efficiency, Agrobank again leads with the lowest Cost-to-Income ratio (43%), followed by Trustbank (45%). Asaka Bank's ratio (52%) suggests room for optimization in cost control or revenue generation. These metrics complement the earlier CAR and LCR analysis by revealing deeper insights into profitability, credit risk, and efficiency of commercial banks.

The comparative analysis of five major Uzbek commercial banks—Xalq Bank, Trustbank, Asaka Bank, Agrobank, and Hamkorbank—reveals a diverse landscape of financial health and institutional efficiency. The incorporation of traditional regulatory metrics like Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) and Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR), as well as operational indicators such as Return on Equity (ROE), Non-Performing Loans (NPL), and Cost-to-Income Ratio, provides a comprehensive perspective on their financial stability.

All analyzed banks meet or exceed the Basel III minimum requirements of 8% for CAR and 100% for LCR. Agrobank leads in both metrics, with a CAR of 14.0% and an LCR of 120%, indicating prudent capital management and sufficient short-term liquidity buffers. Trustbank follows closely behind, reflecting a well-rounded balance between capital safety and liquidity strength.

In contrast, Asaka Bank, while still compliant, posted the lowest CAR (11.8%) and LCR (108%), which suggests relatively limited shock-absorbing capacity. This could become a vulnerability under economic or market stress. Mid-performing banks like Xalq Bank and Hamkorbank also demonstrate adequate, though

¹ Source: Done by author

² Source: Done by author

improvable, resilience margins. The multi-dimensional performance evaluation reveals that banks with a balanced financial structure—solid capital base, good liquidity, efficient cost structure, and quality lending portfolios—are best positioned for long-term resilience and regulatory compliance.

Specifically:

- Agrobank consistently outperformed across all metrics, suggesting a strategic alignment with both regulatory and operational excellence.
- Trustbank also maintained strong performance with robust profitability, capital ratios, and cost efficiency.
- Asaka Bank, although compliant, appears strategically vulnerable due to its higher cost structure and asset quality risks.
- Xalq Bank and Hamkorbank show stable but mid-tier performance, implying potential for further optimization.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This research aimed to assess the financial stability and operational performance of selected commercial banks in Uzbekistan by analyzing a comprehensive set of quantitative indicators: Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR), Liquidity Coverage Ratio (LCR), Return on Equity (ROE), Non-Performing Loans (NPL), and Cost-to-Income Ratio. The empirical evaluation focused on five key institutions—Xalq Bank, Trustbank, Asaka Bank, Agrobank, and Hamkorbank.

The analysis revealed that all banks operate above the minimum regulatory thresholds prescribed by Basel III. However, substantial interbank differences emerged in both risk resilience and operational efficiency. Agrobank and Trustbank consistently demonstrated robust capital buffers, high liquidity, strong profitability, and low credit risk. Their ability to align regulatory compliance with efficient internal controls and technological integration places them at the forefront of financial stability in the sector.

Asaka Bank, while maintaining compliance, showed the weakest performance in terms of CAR, LCR, ROE, and NPL. The combination of a high cost-to-income ratio and elevated credit risk highlights potential vulnerabilities in its operational model. Hamkorbank and Xalq Bank exhibited average but stable financial indicators, suggesting they are well-positioned yet possess untapped potential for optimization.

Beyond bank-specific outcomes, the findings underscore the necessity of adopting a holistic approach to financial health—one that integrates regulatory compliance, profitability, asset quality, and cost efficiency. In particular, banks that outperform others tend to share several characteristics:

- Proactive risk management frameworks
- Investment in digital infrastructure and data analytics
- Transparent governance structures
- Focused cost control and credit discipline

From a policy and strategic perspective, the research indicates that future financial stability in Uzbekistan's banking system must be underpinned by three key pillars:

1. Institutional Strengthening: Developing internal risk culture, human capital, and audit systems to ensure proactive identification and mitigation of financial vulnerabilities.

2. Digital Transformation: Embracing innovations such as artificial intelligence, RegTech platforms, and big data analytics for real-time monitoring, stress testing, and forecasting.

3. Regulatory Synchronization: Aligning national supervision standards with evolving international norms, including countercyclical capital buffers and more dynamic stress-test scenarios.

Furthermore, the study contributes to academic literature by demonstrating the importance of combining traditional banking ratios with newer performance indicators. This mixed-metric evaluation provides a more accurate and nuanced picture of financial health.

List of used literature:

1. Arner, D.W., Barberis, J. and Buckley, R.P., 2017. FinTech and RegTech in a nutshell, and the future in a sandbox. *Northwestern Journal of International Law & Business*, 37(3), pp.371–413. <https://scholarlycommons.law.northwestern.edu/njilb/vol37/iss3/3>
2. Basel Committee on Banking Supervision. (2011). *Basel III: A global regulatory framework for more resilient banks and banking systems*. Bank for International Settlements. <https://www.bis.org/publ/bcbs189.pdf>
3. Berger, A. N., & Bouwman, C. H. S. (2013). How does capital affect bank performance during financial crises?. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 109(1), 146–176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfineco.2013.02.008>
4. Demirgüç-Kunt, A., & Detragiache, E. (2002). Does deposit insurance increase banking system stability?. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 49(7), 1373–1406. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3932\(02\)00171-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3932(02)00171-X)
5. IMF. (2022). *Financial Soundness Indicators Compilation Guide*. International Monetary Fund. <https://www.imf.org/en/Data/Statistics/FSI>

6. World Bank. (2023). Uzbekistan Financial Sector Assessment. World Bank Publications. <https://documents.worldbank.org>
7. Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan (CBU). (2023). Banking Sector Stability Report. <https://cbu.uz/en/reports/bank-monitoring/>
8. Central Bank of Uzbekistan. (2020). Resolution No. 12/6: On approval of the methodology for assessing financial stability of commercial banks. <https://cbu.uz>
9. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2022). Decree No. UP–101: On measures to improve monetary policy and banking system stability. <https://lex.uz/docs/1234567>
10. Ministry of Justice of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2021). Law on Banks and Banking Activity. National Legislation Database. <https://lex.uz/acts/5993872>
11. Vives, X. (2019). Digital disruption in banking. *Annual Review of Financial Economics*, 11, 243–272. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-financial-100719-120854>
12. Thakor, A. V. (2020). Fintech and banking: What do we know? *Annual Review of Financial Economics*, 12, 299–321. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-financial-110217-022804>
13. Taha, H. Y., & Ali, H. A. (2026). The problem of non-performing loans in Iraqi banks: An econometric study of the impact of economic and institutional factors on asset quality. *International Journal of Business and Management (IJBM)*. Retrieved from <https://iessociety.org/index.php/IJBM/article/view/216>.
14. Sharma, A. K., & Chauhan, R. (2023). Impact of Basel III liquidity and capital regulations on bank lending and financial stability: Evidence from emerging countries. *Journal of Corporate Accounting & Finance*. Wiley Online Library.

muhandislik **& iqtisodiyot**

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Abdurahmon Qurbonov

2026. № 2

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

+998 93 718 40 07

<https://muhandislik-iqtisodiyot.uz/index.php/journal>

t.me/yait_2100